

The Influence of Leadership and Career Development on Employee Performance and Work Environment as Intervening Variable (Case Study of Directorate General of Oil and Gas in Indonesia)

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Abstract:- This research aims to determine and analyze the effect of leadership, and career development on employee performance through the work environment as an intervening variable. The research method used at this time is descriptive quantitative. The population of this study were employees of the Directorate General of Oil and Gas with a sample size of 83 respondents. The data analysis method uses SEM-PLS. The results of research and discussion, that show that Leadership and Career Development at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through the Work Environment. This means that solutive leaders improve employee performance by creating a conducive work environment and motivated employees provide productive performance through an organized work environment. Leadership and career development in the Directorate General of Oil and Gas have a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment. This means that leaders who provide solutions to challenges in the work environment can be able to provide comfort in the work environment and employee motivation can be increased by implementing training to help motivate and meet employee needs in gaining insight and knowledge of each employee to provide optimal performance results for the agency. Leadership, career development, and the work environment at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that to provide good employee performance, leaders in achieving organizational goals are expected to provide solutions by fostering, directing, inviting, and motivating employees to work optimally to achieve performance success. This means that motivational needs require planning by management to provide employee motivation needs and a high work environment reflects the level of employee comfort in the place where they work.

Keywords:- Leadership, Work Environment, Career Development, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Petroleum and Natural Gas are crucial commodities that greatly affect modern life and as an important component in industrial development and as the main driver of industry and state development, so their management must be controlled optimally to provide prosperity for the people and the country. The high world oil price has a very positive influence on the country so government revenue in the quarter of 2022 reached 13.95 billion US dollars or around 202 trillion rupiah or around 140% of the Indonesian government's 2022 budget target and around 83% of the 2022 revised state budget target. Because the oil and natural gas sector has a huge impact on the progress of the nation's industry and economy, its activities need to be regulated so that it can provide maximum results for state revenue.

This Directorate General of Oil and Gas in Indonesia is an implementing element of policy formulation and implementation in the field of guidance, monitoring, and control of oil and gas operations. The activities of guidance, monitoring, and control of oil and gas operations need a systematic, productive, and efficient bureaucracy. The Bureaucratic Reform that has been implemented by the Directorate General of Oil and Gas has brought significant changes.

The achievement of the implementation aspect of change can be seen from the strengthening of 8 areas of change, namely the change management area, institutional area, governance area, legislation area, accountability area, supervision area, human resources area, and public service development area. The implementation of Bureaucratic Reform entered the third period with three goals, namely a clean and accountable bureaucracy, capable, and excellent public services.

The Regulation of the *Menteri Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara Dan Reformasi Birokrasi* (Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform) of the Republic of Indonesia Article 1 Number 6, Number 38 of 2018 concerning Measurement of the State Civil Apparatus Professionalism Index states that the employee professionalism index is a statistical measure that describes the quality of employees based on the suitability of qualifications, competence, performance, and employee discipline in carrying out job duties.

Table 1: Calculation of Professionalism Index per Measurement Dimension for 2019-2020

Measurement Dimension								Total	
Qualification (Weight 25%)		Competence (Weight 25%)		Performance (Weight 25%)		Discipline (Weight 25%)			
2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020
15.25	15.61	30.61	27.17	27.33	26.74	4.98	4.97	78.17	74.49

The achievement of the MPI (Main Performance Indicator) of the Employee Professionalism Index in 2020 was 74.49 and did not meet the set target of 75. In each dimension measurement, there was a decrease compared to the realization results in 2019, except for the Qualification dimension where there was an increase of 0.36. A significant decrease occurred in the competency dimension of 3.44. This is closely related to the Covid-19 pandemic, which had a major impact on improving employee competence.

The competency dimension is the largest weight in the calculation of the employee Professionalism Index, which is 40%. Planning for 20 TH (Training Hours) training for employees was carried out to boost this value, which at the beginning of the planning, the implementation of training was scheduled according to the predetermined time. With the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus and the implementation of social distancing in early 2020, the planned training schedule had to be postponed and canceled.

In response to this situation, the training organizers were dealt with by rescheduling the implementation of delayed training using the distance learning method. A significant decrease occurred in employee participation in seminar or workshop activities, where in 2019 it could reach 85.55% while in 2020 it only reached 44.76% or reduced by half. This is closely related to the Covid-19 pandemic, which has an impact on seminar or workshop activities not being carried out due to the application of social distancing to prevent mass gatherings.

In measuring the competency dimension, the fulfillment of 20 TH training is still not thoroughly applied to all employees. The limited quota for training participation certainly cannot cover all employee training needs each year, and the implementation of seminars or workshops is very less than the previous year due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Employee performance measurement is also less monitored by superiors so that employee performance achievements are not maximized. In addition, there are still violations of employee discipline, although it does not affect significantly, of course it is hoped that the Directorate General of Oil and Gas will be clean from disciplinary violations.

As preliminary data, researchers have conducted a pre-survey by randomly distributing questionnaires to 30 employees at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas, respondents are invited to provide 3 answers that are considered to affect employee performance. showing the

results of the pre-survey of employee responses regarding factors that affect performance and their impact on employee performance, it is known that Work Environment, Leadership, and career development are indicators that need to be considered and given special attention so that the employee Professionalism Index can be improved and reach the target.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Performance

Performance is the result of work and work behavior carried out in carrying out the duties and responsibilities given in a certain time [1]. Performance is the result of work or work productivity both in quality and quantity achieved by a person or work team in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities given by the organization [2].

B. Work Environment

The work environment is the overall materials and tools faced, the surrounding environment in which a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both individually and in groups [3]. The work environment is the condition or atmosphere or around the workplace location. The work environment can be in the form of layout, facilities, infrastructure, and space, as well as relationships with colleagues [1].

C. Leadership

Leadership is a method used by a leader in influencing employees to carry out their duties and obligations as expected based on predetermined goals [4]. Leadership is the behavior of a leader in regulating, managing and ordering his subordinates to carry out the tasks and responsibilities he assigns [1].

D. Career Development

Career Development is an effort carried out by every employee or organization to spur himself to do his best in serving and improving his abilities or skills in the implementation of the main tasks and functions of profit and non-profit organizations and all work [4]. Training or career development is the process of training and equipping employees by improving their skills, abilities, knowledge and behavior. Individuals who develop will provide optimal performance, namely showing good work results. Organizations and leaders as entities that provide career opportunities by providing clear career paths to achieve organizational goals. Professional career development activities are important to improve employee performance [1].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the literature review, the following terms of reference were developed in this study:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

In this writing hypothesis, the author concludes that it is suspected:

- H1 : Leadership affects the Work Environment
- H2: Career Development affects the Work Environment
- H3 : Leadership affects employee performance.
- H4: Work Environment affects Employee Performance.
- H5: Career Development affects Employee Performance.
- H6 : Leadership affects employee performance through work environment
- H7 : Career Development affects Employee Performance through Work Environment

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

The author uses a quantitative descriptive method, namely on a survey scale to state the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable or dependent variable. The scale used to measure the variables is using an ordinal scale, while scoring using a Likert scale. The author distributed questionnaires to 82 employees using purposive sampling technique. This data research analysis uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method to validate measurements and structural models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample used in this study was 83 respondents, namely employees of the Directorate General of Oil and Gas with data collection in the form of distributing questionnaires. Respondent's statements are expected to be able to provide an overview of the conditions at the research location. In this study, the analysis of respondents' descriptions was grouped according to length of work, education, gender, and age. The analysis process is carried out using the PLS program calculation with SmartPLS version 3.2.9. After that, the calculation results can be seen in the excel report.

A. Convergent Validity

Outer loading > 0.7 is the recommended value and outer loading of 0.5 - 0.6 is still acceptable, but if the outer loading value < 0.5 in the measurement model calculation will be excluded [5]. Based on this theory, the researcher took a value of 0.6 and for a value of 0.5 - 0.6 it is still acceptable.

Based on the results of the PLS model estimation that has been processed, it can be seen that all indicators on all constructs have a loading factor value above 0.6 so all PLS model indicators are declared to meet the requirements of convergent validity. The loading factor value of each indicator and the AVE value on all constructs are presented in the following table:

Table 2: Results of Loading Factor and AVE

Variables	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Leadership	KP1	0.836	0.692
	KP2	0.887	
	KP3	0.740	
	KP4	0.867	
	KP5	0.829	
	KP6	0.848	
	KP7	0.828	
	KP8	0.819	
Performance	KIN1	0.799	0.694
	KIN2	0.864	
	KIN3	0.900	
	KIN4	0.728	
	KIN5	0.894	
	KIN6	0.819	
	KIN7	0.893	
	KIN8	0.737	
Work Environment	LK1	0.697	0.690
	LK2	0.819	
	LK3	0.831	
	LK4	0.884	
	LK5	0.876	
	LK6	0.864	
Career Development	PK1	0.869	0.686
	PK2	0.807	
	PK3	0.750	
	PK4	0.881	
	PK5	0.854	
	PK6	0.728	
	PK7	0.871	
	PK8	0.770	
	PK9	0.903	

Based on the results of the PLS analysis in the table above, it can be seen that all indicators have a loading factor > 0.6 and all constructs have AVE > 0.5, which means that all indicators are valid and all constructs meet the requirements for convergent validity criteria.

B. Discriminant Validity

In PLS analysis, discriminant validity is used to ensure that each concept of all latent variables is different from other variables. PLS analysis for testing discriminant validity is carried out through three methods, namely by assessing cross loading, the Fornell-Larcker method and using the HTMT method [6]. In this study, validity testing was carried out using cross loading indicators and the Fornell-Larcker method.

Table 3: Indicator Cross Loading Results

	Leadership	Performance	Work Environment	Career Development
KIN1	0.573	0.799	0.518	0.462
KIN2	0.598	0.864	0.581	0.620
KIN3	0.587	0.900	0.639	0.660
KIN4	0.421	0.728	0.563	0.519
KIN5	0.687	0.894	0.615	0.678
KIN6	0.553	0.819	0.505	0.491
KIN7	0.581	0.893	0.583	0.460
KIN8	0.316	0.737	0.498	0.344
KP1	0.836	0.534	0.459	0.510
KP2	0.887	0.577	0.459	0.447
KP3	0.740	0.486	0.445	0.457
KP4	0.867	0.721	0.530	0.534
KP5	0.829	0.411	0.359	0.411
KP6	0.848	0.455	0.347	0.523

	Leadership	Performance	Work Environment	Career Development
KP7	0.828	0.486	0.321	0.330
KP8	0.819	0.619	0.518	0.506
LK1	0.349	0.461	0.697	0.481
LK2	0.462	0.490	0.819	0.576
LK3	0.411	0.450	0.831	0.506
LK4	0.417	0.541	0.884	0.543
LK5	0.463	0.669	0.876	0.598
LK6	0.512	0.706	0.864	0.652
PK1	0.501	0.546	0.612	0.869
PK2	0.306	0.500	0.547	0.807
PK3	0.392	0.470	0.390	0.750
PK4	0.513	0.583	0.680	0.881
PK5	0.542	0.598	0.564	0.854
PK6	0.423	0.436	0.431	0.728
PK7	0.484	0.516	0.560	0.871
PK8	0.428	0.436	0.482	0.770
PK9	0.575	0.687	0.703	0.903

From the table above, it can be seen that the loading factor value on all indicators is greater than the cross loading value. So this shows that all indicators of this study are valid.

In testing validity using the Fornell Larker method, the construct has met the discriminant validity criteria if the

construct's correlation with other constructs does not exceed the construct's AVE square root value, while in testing discriminant validity using the cross loading method, the construct is declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the indicators in the construct has the highest value in the construct and not in other constructs [6].

Table 4: Fornell Larcker results

	KP	KIN	LK	PK
KP	0.833			
KIN	0.662	0.832		
LK	0.530	0.679	0.831	
PK	0.565	0.649	0.680	0.828

The discriminant validity test results in the table above are the results of the Fornell-Larcker method. Based on the test results, it can be seen that all indicators and constructs in the PLS model are declared to meet the required discriminant validity criteria, it can be seen that for example the performance variable, the AVE root value of the performance construct (KIN) is 0.915, while the correlation

between the performance construct and other constructs does not exceed 0.915 (0.902 for the work discipline construct; 0.904 for the work environment construct and 0.890 for the motivation construct) so that it is stated that the performance construct is by the discriminant validity criteria of the Fornell Larcker method.

Table 5: Construct Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Leadership	0.937	0.948
Performance	0.936	0.947
Work Environment	0.909	0.930
Career Development	0.942	0.951

The table above shows the results of the composite reliability test that all latent variable values have Cronbach's

alpha and composite reliability values ≥ 0.60 . That way all the reliability constructs are acceptable.

C. Test Coefficient of Determination (R-Squared)

Table 6: Results of R-Square Value

Variable	R Square
PERFORMANCE (Y)	0.609
WORK ENVIRONMENT (Z)	0.493

From the table above, it is known that the R-Square (R2) value or the coefficient of determination of the performance construct is 0.609. These results indicate that

the Performance variable can be explained by the Leadership, Work Environment and Career Development variables by 60.9% (medium) while the rest is explained by

other exogenous variables outside this study. Other results show that the Work Environment variable can be explained by the Leadership, and Career Development variables by 49.3% (medium) while the remaining R-Square value is explained by other exogenous variables outside this study.

The value used to see the size of the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables, where the F-Square values of 0.02 0.15 and 0.35 are interpreted as small, medium, and large influences at the structural level [6].

D. F-Square Test

Table 7: Results of F-Square Value

	KP (X1)	PK (X2)	LK (Z)	KIN (Y)
KP (X1)			0.061	0.212
PK (X2)			0.419	0.055
LK (Z)				0.154
KIN Z				

Based on the table above, the effect size F-Square on each exogenous variable on the endogenous variable is explained as follows:

- Leadership variable (X1) on the Work Environment variable (Z) has an F² of 0.061, which means that the Leadership variable (X1) has little effect.
- Career Development variable (X2) on the Work Environment variable (Z) has an F² of 0.419, which means that the Career Development variable (X2) has a big influence.
- Leadership variable (X1) on the Performance variable (Y) has an F² of 0.212, which means that the Leadership variable (X1) has a moderate influence.

- Career Development variable (X2) on the Performance variable (Y) has an F² of 0.055, which means that the Career Development variable (X2) has little effect.
- Work Environment variable (Z) on the employee performance variable (Y) has an F² of 0.154, which means that the Work Environment variable (Z) has a moderate influence.

E. Predictive Relevance Test (Q-Squared)

This statistic is obtained by a sample reuse technique called "Blindfolding" where the removal distance is set between 5 and 10, and where the number of observations divided by the removal distance is not an integer [7]. Predictive Relevance (Q-Squared) results are said to be good if the value is > 0.

Table 8: Q-Squared Results

	SSO	SSE	Q ²
LEADERSHIP	664.000	664.000	
CAREER DEVELOPMENT	747.000	747.000	
WORK ENVIRONMENT	498.000	350.923	0.295
PERFORMANCE	664.000	420.458	0.367

Based on the table above, the Q-Squared results can be said to be good because all values above > 0.

mean square residual (SRMR) and the normal fit index (NFI). The model is considered to have a good fit if the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) value is below 0.10 [7].

F. Model Fit Test

In this study, the fit model evaluation was carried out using two testing models, namely the standardized root

Table 9: Model Fit Test Results

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.083	0.083
d_ ULS	3.456	3.456
d_ G	2.635	2.635
Chi-Square	951.784	951.784
NFI	0.675	0.675

Based on the table above, the results show that the model in this study has a good fit because the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) is below the value of 0.10 and the normal fit index (NFI) shows that this research model is 67.5% (0.675).

whereas if the t-value is smaller than t-table then the hypothesis is rejected, besides it is necessary to see the p-value as an indication of significance if the p-value is <0.05 then it is significant. Through testing the path coefficient, the strength of the relationship between variables can be described. The results of data processing can be seen in the following table:

G. Path Coefficient Testing and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing carried out in this study will result in an accepted hypothesis if the t-value is greater than t-table,

Table 10: Test Results of Path Coefficient Direct Effects

	Sample Original	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
LEADERSHIP -> PERFORMANCE	0.359	0.356	0.104	3.468	0.001
LEADERSHIP -> WORK ENVIRONMENT	0.214	0.224	0.086	2.500	0.013
WORK ENVIRONMENT -> PERFORMANCE	0.345	0.349	0.107	3.233	0.001
CAREER DEVELOPMENT -> PERFORMANCE	0.212	0.216	0.107	1.974	0.049
CAREER DEVELOPMENT -> WORK ENVIRONMENT	0.559	0.555	0.075	7.437	0.000

Table 11: Test Results of Total Indirect Effects.

	Sample Original	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
KEPEMIMPINAN -> KINERJA	0.074	0.077	0.037	1.966	0.050
PENGEMBANGAN KARIR -> KINERJA	0.193	0.194	0.068	2.847	0.005

Hypothesis 1 explains that H1 is accepted, which means that Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment. This shows that good leadership can provide comfort in the work environment.

The most influential thing is to help solve employee problems. The work environment in an organization or company requires the role of a leader so that the organization can take place properly. Leaders who can create a pleasant work environment atmosphere can produce a work environment where employees come to their workplace with a sense of satisfaction.

Leaders who organize, assign detailed tasks to their employees in an inclusive manner can create employee work efficiency in a conducive work environment. Leaders who regard themselves as colleagues to their subordinates can give a very positive workplace impression that supports each other in progressive productivity.

Hypothesis 2 explains that H2 is accepted, which means that Career Development has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment. This shows that good career development can provide a conducive work environment.

The most influential thing is the increase in motivation among employees. The role of employees to create a conducive work environment requires training and motivation supported by management by meeting employee training needs and planting a productive work culture following the vision of the organization. If training and motivation are not supported and not given to employees, it can have consequences of low trust, unhealthy competition among employees which provides an unfavorable work environment and is detrimental to the organization to be productive.

Hypothesis 3 explains that H3 is accepted, which means that leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance. This shows that good leadership can improve employee performance.

The most influential thing is helping to solve employee problems. To realize good employee performance, there are various probabilities that leaders can carry out with accurate actions. The importance of the leader's role to achieve organizational goals in improving employee performance in carrying out their duties. As for employees, it is not enough just to work well, leaders are needed to direct, invite, motivate, be able to help solve problems to develop the ability and consolidate each employee to develop and work optimally. Therefore, it can be said that a leader is the driving force behind the success of employee performance in an organization.

The results of hypothesis 3 are in line with Leadership plays a very important role in the success of an organization in carrying out its various functions, especially seen in the performance of employees [8].

Hypothesis 4 explains that H4 is accepted, which means that career development has a positive and significant effect on performance. This shows that the better career development is applied, the more productive employee performance will be.

The most influential thing is the increase in motivation among employees. To improve employee performance, agencies can motivate employees by providing opportunities to develop their abilities and knowledge, this can be assisted by the implementation of 20 JP training and seminars held. The implementation of training helps meet the needs and motivation of employees in gaining insight and knowledge of each employee to provide optimal performance results for the agency. In principle, career development includes long-term planning in improving the quality of employee

performance, so agencies should provide sustainable and planned employee career guidance.

Hypothesis 5 explains that H5 is accepted, which means that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance. This shows that a good work environment supports good employee performance. This shows that the work environment at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas is optimal and supports employee performance.

The thing that most influences is the guaranteed security conditions that increase the enthusiasm for completing work. It is known in this study that the work environment in an agency can affect the performance of the employees themselves. Performance can increase if employees feel comfortable and safe in their work environment, and in the end employees can work more optimally and increase work productivity. The hope is that each agency manages the work environment properly and safely so that it is hoped that each employee will feel comfortable at work so that they can work at an optimal level and that increased employee performance can increase work productivity. A high working environment reflects the level of comfort of employees in the place where they work.

The results of hypothesis 5 are in line with a good work environment that can trigger employee productivity and performance. The benefit of the work environment is to create a work passion, so that productivity and work performance increase, the work environment can also affect job satisfaction [8].

Hypothesis 6 explains that H6 is accepted, which means that leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance through the work environment. This shows that good leaders improve employee performance by creating a conducive work environment.

The most influential thing is to help solve employee problems. The positive influence of management or leaders on performance can produce flexibility in employee skills and adaptability, the positive effect of a good leader provides optimal employee adaptation and ultimately provides productive employee performance.

Hypothesis 7 explains that H7 is accepted, which means that career development has a positive and significant effect on performance through the work environment. This shows that optimal career development provides productive performance through an organized work environment.

The most influential thing is the increase in motivation among employees. An innovative work environment in providing productive performance requires effective communication, effective communication requires ongoing training to meet the needs of dynamic employees who provide good performance. Good performance can result from communicative employee behavior through training supported by stakeholders following the vision of the organization, thus career development programs such as the Communication Skill Training program can improve employee communication in a work environment that has

the potential to contribute to increasing employee performance productivity.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

- Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, the researcher can provide suggestions, because this research still has several limitations in several aspects so improvements need to be made in further research, including:
- For Directorate General of Oil and Gas, the results of this study can be used as development material regarding more effective human resources and encourage these agencies to optimize their duties and functions to improve employee performance. As for what must be considered to improve employee performance, there are several things as follows:
- Leadership at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely helping to solve employee problems. It can be concluded that leaders who provide solutions to challenges in the work environment can be able to provide comfort in the work environment. By providing solutive information for employees, it is expected to be able to provide a good working environment so that the organization or company can run well.
- Career Development in Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on the Work Environment. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely increasing motivation among employees. It can be concluded that employee motivation can be increased by implementing training to help motivate and meet the needs of employees in gaining insight and knowledge of each employee to provide optimal performance results for the agency.
- Leadership at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely helping to solve employee problems. It can be concluded that to provide good employee performance, leaders in achieving organizational goals are expected to provide solutions by fostering, directing, inviting, and motivating employees to work optimally in achieving successful performance in the organization.
- Career Development in Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely increased motivation among employees. It can be concluded that motivational needs require planning by management to provide employee motivation needs. In principle, career development includes long-term planning in improving the quality of employee performance, therefore agencies should carry out employee career guidance which is carried out in a planned and sustainable manner.
- The work environment at the Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. It is known in this study that the work environment in an agency can affect the performance of the employees themselves. Referring to the highest

loading factor value, namely guaranteed security conditions that increase the enthusiasm for completing work. With good work environment management, including guaranteed security conditions, employees are expected to feel comfortable at work so that they can work at an optimal level and increased employee performance can increase work productivity. A high working environment reflects the level of comfort of employees in the place where they work.

- Leadership in Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through the Work Environment. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely helping to solve employee problems. It can be seen that solutive leaders improve employee performance by creating a conducive work environment. The positive influence of management or leaders on performance can result in the flexibility of employee skills and adaptability, the positive effect of a good leader provides optimal employee adaptation to ultimately provide productive employee performance.
- Career Development in Directorate General of Oil and Gas has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance through the Work Environment. Referring to the highest loading factor value, namely increased motivation among employees. This shows that motivated employees provide productive performance through an organized work environment. An innovative work environment in providing productive performance requires effective communication, effective communication requires ongoing training to meet the needs of dynamic employees who provide good performance. Good performance can result from communicative employee behavior through stakeholder-supported training following the organization's vision, thus career development programs such as the Communication Skill Training program can improve employee communication in a work environment that has the potential to contribute to improving employee performance productivity.

As for suggestions for future research, this study has limitations and shortcomings. It can be seen from 39.1% that the performance variable is influenced by other variables or factors outside of leadership, work environment and career development, so other variables can be suggested to be the next research. And 50.7% of Work Environment variables are influenced by other variables or factors outside of Leadership and Career Development, so other variables can be suggested to be the next research.

The author suggests further research to re-examine the relationship between the direct influence of leadership, career development, and work environment on employee performance. The author also suggests that future research add other variables that are known to be able to influence performance variables such as organizational culture variables, job satisfaction, work motivation, leadership style, and competence.

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